

Efficient Anomaly Detection in Surveillance Videos Using Pre-Trained CNNs and Self-Supervised Learning

BS Thesis

by

NAEEM YOUSAF

CIIT/FA19-BSE-031/SWL

COMSATS University Islamabad

Pakistan

SPRING 2023

Efficient Anomaly Detection in Surveillance Videos Using Pre-Trained CNNs and Self-Supervised Learning

A thesis submitted to
COMSATS University Islamabad, Sahiwal Campus

In partial fulfillment of the
requirements for the degree of

Bachelor of Science

in

Software Engineering

by

Naeem Yousaf

CIIT/FA19-BSE-031/SWL

Department of Computer Science

COMSATS University Islamabad

Pakistan

SPRING 2023

Efficient Anomaly Detection in Surveillance Videos Using Pre-Trained CNNs and Self-Supervised Learning

This thesis is submitted to the Department of Computer Science in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Bachelor of Science in Software Engineering.

Name	Registration Number
Naeem Yousaf	CIIT/FA19-BSE-031/SWL

Supervisory Committee

Supervisor

Dr. Muhammad Shoaib

Assistant Professor

Department of Computer Science

COMSATS University Islamabad (CUI)

Sahiwal Campus

Co-Supervisor

Muhammad Umar

Lecturer

Department of Computer Science

COMSATS University Islamabad (CUI)

Sahiwal Campus

Certificate of Approval

This thesis is titled.

Efficient Anomaly Detection in Surveillance Videos
Using Pre-Trained CNNs and Self-Supervised Learning

By

Naeem Yousaf

CIIT/FA19-BSE-031/SWL

has been approved.

for the Degree of BS Software Engineering at

COMSATS University Islamabad, Sahiwal Campus

External Examiner:

Supervisor:

Dr. Muhammad Shoaib

Assistant Professor

Department of Computer Science

CUI, Sahiwal Campus

Head of Department:

Dr. Tariq Ali

Department of Computer Science

CUI, Sahiwal Campus

Author's Declaration

I Naeem Yousaf, CIIT/FA19-BSE-031/SWL, hereby declare that I have produced the work presented in this thesis, during the scheduled period of study. I also declare that I have not taken any material from any source except referred to wherever due to that amount of plagiarism is within an acceptable range. If a violation of HEC rules on research has occurred in this thesis, I shall be liable to punishable action under the plagiarism rules of HEC.

Date: _____

Naeem Yousaf

CIIT/FA19-BSE-031/SWL

Certificate

It is certified that Naeem Yousaf, CIIT/FA19-BSE-031/SWL, has carried out all the work related to this thesis under my supervision at the Department of Computer Science, COMSATS University Islamabad, Sahiwal Campus and the work fulfill the requirements for the award of the degree of BS in Software Engineering.

Date: _____

Supervisor:

Dr. Muhammad Shoaib

Assistant Professor

Department of Computer Science

CUI, Sahiwal Campus

Dedication

This thesis is lovingly dedicated to the memory of my late father, whose strength, wisdom, and sacrifices continue to inspire me every day. To my beloved brother, who has been a constant source of encouragement and companionship through every challenge, and to my mother and sister, whose unwavering love, prayers, and support have been my foundation. Without their guidance, patience, and faith in me, this accomplishment would not have been possible. Each page of this work is a testament to their presence in my life, their dreams for me, and the profound impact they have had on shaping the person I am today. I hope to make them proud with this humble effort.

Acknowledgements

First, I am profoundly grateful to Almighty Allah for granting me the strength, determination, and wisdom to undertake and successfully complete this research work.

I wish to express my deepest appreciation to my supervisor, Dr. Muhammad Shoaib, Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science, COMSATS University Islamabad, Sahiwal Campus, for his invaluable guidance, continuous support, and encouragement throughout the course of my research and thesis writing. His insightful feedback and constructive criticism enhanced the quality of this work and helped me overcome numerous challenges.

I am also sincerely thankful to my co-supervisor, Muhammad Umar, Lecturer, for his expert advice, technical input, and unwavering support at every stage of this project. His profound knowledge and thoughtful suggestions played a pivotal role in shaping my research direction.

I would like to extend my gratitude to all the faculty members and staff of the Department of Computer Science, COMSATS University Islamabad, Sahiwal Campus, for providing a supportive academic environment and access to essential resources during my BS studies.

I am deeply indebted to my parents and family for their unconditional love, patience, moral support, and continuous prayers. Their belief in me has been my source of strength, especially during difficult times.

Finally, I acknowledge all those, named and unnamed, who contributed in any way to the successful completion of this thesis. Without their support and encouragement, this accomplishment would not have been possible.

Naeem Yousaf

CIIT/FA19-BSE-031/SWL

Abstract

Efficient Anomaly Detection in Surveillance Videos Using Pre-Trained CNNs and Self-Supervised Learning

By
Naeem Yousaf

The fast growth of surveillance systems in both public and non-public spaces has led to the creation of large amounts of video data, whose manual surveillance becomes inefficient and unreliable. Automated video anomaly detection has thus evolved to be an important topic area in computer vision and that seeks to detect rare, unexpected, and even dangerous events in real time. Nevertheless, most of the current techniques use labelled anomaly data or computationally complex architectures, so they have a limited generalization capability and can only be used in real-world surveillance settings.

This thesis presents Efficient-VAD, a self-supervised video anomaly detection model that is able to reach high accuracy and yet is a real-time model. The suggested system uses the pretrained MobileNetV3-Large network to extract spatial features efficiently and a memory augmented LSTM autoencoder to classify normal behavioural patterns of space and time using video data that is unlabelled. The distinctiveness of abnormal occurrences by observing patterns that do not conform to the usual representations of normal objects leads to the detection of the abnormal objects by the framework by raising reconstruction errors in cases where abnormal objects are observed to deviate.

The comprehensive experiments of the UCF-Crime dataset prove the efficiency of the suggested strategy, with an AUC-ROC of 0.9861 in the severe conditions of class imbalance. Moreover, Efficient-VAD is applicable to real-time and resource-intensive surveillance environments with a low 512 MB memory footprint and a rate of 87.51 frames per second. These findings confirm that the integration of self-supervised learning and memory-enhanced temporal model in conjunction with lightweight CNN backbones offer users a powerful, scalable, and deployment-friendly model to detect video anomalies.

Keywords: Video anomaly detection, self-supervised learning, memory-augmented autoencoder, MobileNetV3, temporal localization, edge deployment, real-time inference.

Table of Contents

Chapter 1	1
Introduction.....	1
1.1 Background and Motivation	1
1.2 Problem Statement.....	2
1.3 Research Challenges	3
1.4 Research Objectives.....	3
1.5 Research Questions.....	4
1.6 Significance	4
1.6.1 Scientific Significance	4
1.6.2 Practical Significance.....	5
1.7 Thesis Organization	5
Chapter 2	6
Literature Review	6
2.1 Traditional Approaches to Video Anomaly Detection	7
2.2 Supervised Learning Approaches	8
2.3 Unsupervised Learning Approaches	10
2.4 Self-Supervised Learning Approaches.....	11
2.5 Feature Extraction and Representation Learning.....	13
2.6 Memory-Augmented Neural Networks	15
2.7 Temporal Modelling and Sequence Learning.....	17
2.8 Threshold Selection and Decision Boundaries	18
2.9 Datasets and Benchmarks	19
2.10 Real-Time and Efficient Systems	21
2.11 Comparison of State-of-the-Art Methods	22
2.12 Research Gaps and Limitations Identified in Existing Work.....	25
Chapter 3	27

Materials and Methods.....	27
3.1 Dataset	27
3.1.1 Dataset Selection.....	27
3.1.2 Dataset Description.....	27
3.1.3 Dataset Preprocessing	27
3.1.4 Data Splitting Strategy	28
3.2 System Architecture Overview	28
3.3 Feature Extraction Methodology	29
3.3.1 Feature Extractor Selection.....	29
3.3.2 Feature Extraction Process.....	29
3.3.3 Feature Consistency and Validation.....	29
3.4 Model Architecture	29
3.4.1 Encoder	30
3.4.2 Memory Module	31
3.4.3 Decoder.....	32
3.4.4 Complete Forward Pass	32
3.4.5 Hyperparameters	32
3.5 Training Methodology	33
3.5.1 Loss Functions	33
3.5.2 Training Procedure.....	34
3.5.3 Training Hyperparameters	35
3.5.4 Training Implementation Details	35
3.6 Inference Pipeline	36
3.6.1 Feature Loading and Preprocessing.....	36
3.6.2 Window-Based Inference.....	36
3.6.3 Temporal Score Aggregation	36
3.6.4 Decision Strategy	36
3.6.5 Output Artifacts.....	37

3.6.6 Inference Configuration	37
3.7 Evaluation Methodology.....	37
3.7.1 Evaluation Metrics	37
3.7.2 Evaluation Procedure	38
3.7.3 Visual and Diagnostic Analysis	38
3.7.4 Efficiency Evaluation.....	39
3.7.5 Evaluation Implementation Details	39
3.8 Experimental Setup.....	39
3.8.1 Hardware Configuration.....	39
3.8.2 Software Configuration.....	39
3.8.3 Configuration and Reproducibility	39
3.9 Graphical User Interface	40
Chapter 4	41
Results and Discussion	41
4.1 Overall Performance Metrics	41
4.2 Detailed Classification Analysis	42
4.2.1 Confusion Matrix Analysis	43
4.3 Efficiency Evaluation.....	43
4.3.1 Computational Performance	43
4.3.2 Efficiency Analysis	44
4.3.3 Benchmark Comparison.....	44
4.4 Comparison with State-of-the-Art Methods	45
4.5 Qualitative Results and Visualizations.....	46
4.5.1 ROC Curve Analysis	46
4.5.2 Precision-Recall Curve Analysis.....	46
4.5.3 Score Distribution Analysis	47
4.5.4 Confusion Matrix Visualization	47
4.5.5 Frame-Level Anomaly Detection.....	48
4.5.6 t-SNE Visualization.....	49

4.6 Discussion.....	49
Chapter 5.....	51
Conclusion.....	51
References.....	52

List of Figures

Figure 1.1: Evolution of Video Surveillance Systems	2
Figure 3.1: System architecture of the proposed Efficient-VAD system	28
Figure 3.2: Self-Supervised Training Flow Using Normal Data	30
Figure 4.1: ROC curve for Efficient-VAD on UCF-Crime Subset dataset.	45
Figure 4.2: Precision-Recall curve demonstrating detection performance.	46
Figure 4.3: Histogram of anomaly scores for normal and abnormal videos.	46
Figure 4.4: Confusion matrix showing true versus predicted video classes.	47
Figure 4.5: Frame-level anomaly score progression for an Anomaly video.	47
Figure 4.6: Frame-level anomaly score progression for a normal video.	48
Figure 4.7: t-SNE plot showing clustering of normal and abnormal video embeddings.	48

List of Tables

Table 2.1: Literature review summary of anomaly detection methods in surveillance videos.	22
Table 3.1: Training Hyperparameters of the Efficient-VAD Model	35
Table 4.1: Overall performance metrics of Efficient-VAD on the UCF-Crime dataset, including AUC-ROC, accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and optimal threshold.	40
Table 4.2: Per-class performance of Efficient-VAD for normal and abnormal classes, showing precision, recall, F1-score, and support.	41
Table 4.3: Confusion matrix of Efficient-VAD on the UCF-Crime test set, showing true positives, false positives, true negatives, and false negatives.	42
Table 4.4: Efficiency evaluation of Efficient-VAD compared to baseline methods, including inference time, FPS, and memory consumption.	43
Table 4.5: Comparison of Efficient-VAD with state-of-the-art video anomaly detection methods on the UCF-Crime dataset.	44

List of Abbreviations

AUC Area Under the Curve

CNN Convolutional Neural Network

FPS Frames Per Second

GPU Graphics Processing Unit

LSTM Long Short-Term Memory

MSE Mean Squared Error

ROC Receiver Operating Characteristic

CPU Central Processing Unit

Chapter 1

Introduction

The fast development of surveillance systems in both public and private has expanded access to video data as a security and monitoring tool. Although these systems are necessary to keep safety, continuous video streams still represent a significant challenge to be effectively analysed. Surveillance footage cannot be monitored manually, and with a high level of accuracy, as well as at scale. This means that there is a great demand for smart, computerized methods of video analysis that can detect abnormal incidents precisely and promptly. Video Anomaly Detection (VAD) has thus become a significant field of study in the field of computer vision, which seeks to identify abnormal behaviour in surveillance video footage without always involving human effort.

1.1 Background and Motivation

The widespread use of surveillance cameras in towns, transport systems, shopping centres, and other infrastructures has led to the creation of huge amounts of video data. These systems run 24 hours around the clock, generating video frames on a large scale that would be hard to examine by hand. Human operators are restrained by exhaustion, decreased alertness and the inability to observe several feeds of the camera at the same time, and it usually results in sluggish reaction or lack of essential occurrences [1].

Video Anomaly Detection aims at automatic detection of events or actions that are not within the pattern. In the real-world surveillance, anomalies can be violent behaviour, stealing, accidents, unauthorized access, or any other suspicious behaviour. The necessity to detect such events is the key to effective security management and safety of people [2].

Nonetheless, detecting anomalies is a difficult task involved because of the nature of abnormal events. Normal activities are usually even and repetitive in nature whereas anomalies are few, varied and in many cases unpredictable. This is not possible or practicable to label all possible abnormal events. Conventional supervised methods of learning hence fail to work in real-life surveillance scenarios [3].

Figure 1.1: Evolution of Video Surveillance Systems

This figure 1.1 demonstrates how video anomaly detection systems have developed, beginning with human surveillance, rule-based systems, handcrafted feature-based machine learning, deep learning, and specially supervised learning techniques.

The latest deep learning, especially self-supervised learning and transfer learning, have given some promising solutions to these problems. Self-supervised learning provides the ability of the models to learn representations without any non-normal data, which is universally available in the surveillance domain [4]. Simultaneously, there are lightweight convolutional neural networks like MobileNetV3, which can extract features with high efficiency with a low cost of computation. Such advances encourage the creation of scalable, efficient, and generalizable video anomaly detectors to be used in the real-world environment.

1.2 Problem Statement

Even though the video anomaly detection has made a lot of progress, currently there are several limitations to the application of the current methods in the actual surveillance setup. Most of the supervised strategies are based on a substantial quantity of the labelled anomaly data that is challenging, expensive and even unfeasible to find because abnormal events are unusual and unpredictable. Moreover, the models which are trained in types of anomalies usually do not generalize the unknown or new abnormal behaviours. Most state-of-the-art deep learning algorithms also utilize computationally intensive structures, so they are not suitable in terms of real-time processing and execution on resource-constrained processors. Moreover, good modelling of temporal relationships in video information has been an exceedingly difficult task but the key to the correct differentiation between normal and abnormal behaviours. These drawbacks present the necessity to have a highly efficient, self-monitored, and time-conscious video anomaly detection system capable of functioning in a high-confidence way in realistic surveillance settings.

1.3 Research Challenges

Developing the proposed self-supervised, memory-augmented video anomaly detection model involves several research-specific challenges that directly affect system performance and reliability. The key challenges faced with this research are outlined below:

- **Learning Normal Behaviour with Limited Supervision:** Training the model using only normal video data requires careful design to ensure that the learned representations accurately capture diverse normal behaviour patterns without overfitting.
- **Balancing Efficiency and Accuracy:** Integrating lightweight feature extraction (MobileNetV3) with temporal modelling must achieve a balance between computational efficiency and anomaly detection accuracy, particularly for real-time surveillance scenarios.
- **Effective Memory Module Design:** Designing a memory mechanism that reliably stores representative normal patterns while preventing contamination from anomalous inputs is a critical challenge.
- **Temporal Dependency Modelling:** Capturing both short-term and long-term temporal dependencies in video sequences using an LSTM-based autoencoder is essential yet challenging, especially in complex and crowded scenes.
- **Robust Anomaly Scoring:** Defining a stable and discriminative anomaly scoring strategy based on reconstruction error that generalizes well across different anomaly types and video conditions remains a non-trivial task.

1.4 Research Objectives

The main objective of this research is to develop an efficient and reliable self-supervised video anomaly detection system for surveillance applications. The specific research objectives are clearly stated as follows:

1. To learn and model normal activity patterns from unlabelled surveillance videos using a self-supervised learning approach.
2. To perform computationally efficient spatial feature extraction from video frames using a pretrained MobileNetV3 network.
3. To capture short-term and long-term temporal dependencies in video sequences using a memory-augmented LSTM-based architecture for accurate anomaly detection.

4. To enable real-time or near real-time anomaly detection while operating under limited computational resources.

1.5 Research Questions

Based on the research problem and objectives, this study seeks to address the following research questions:

Q1. How can a self-supervised learning framework be designed to effectively model normal behaviour patterns in surveillance videos without using labelled anomaly data?

Q2. How can lightweight pretrained CNN architecture be utilized to extract discriminative features while maintaining computational efficiency?

Q3. How can temporal dependencies in video sequences be modelled to improve the accuracy and robustness of anomaly detection?

Q4. How can real-time anomaly detection performance be achieved in practical surveillance environments with limited computational resources?

1.6 Significance

The importance of this study can be considered both scientifically and practically. This study has filled the gap in the research on intelligent surveillance by overcoming the main weaknesses of the current video anomaly detection methods as well as providing the solution that can be implemented in the real world.

1.6.1 Scientific Significance

Scientifically, this study will be relevant to computer vision since it will suggest an effective self-supervised video anomaly detection model that is independent of labelled anomaly example. The combination of pretrained lightweight CNN-based spatial feature extraction and memory-augmented LSTM-based temporal modelling gives a powerful system of learning normal behaviour patterns in video sequences. This study establishes that performance of competitive anomaly detection can be realized while it is computationally efficient and thus one of the fundamental research gaps between accuracy-oriented and efficiency-oriented methods can be resolved. What is more, the research reinforces the interpretation of the fact that memory-based architecture may boost the process of learning the temporal representation in anomaly detection tasks.

1.6.2 Practical Significance

In practical terms, the suggested system will address the needs of real-life surveillance settings. Its computational efficiency allows real-time or near real-time computations, allowing it to be used on resource constrained computers like edge computers and embedded computers. The capability to find out unseen anomalies of the past enhances greater system resiliency and reliability in dynamically monitored cases. Besides, the proposed framework can be adopted, extended, and integrated into existing surveillance infrastructures by researchers and practitioners due to its modular and reproducible design.

1.7 Thesis Organization

This thesis is organized into five chapters. Chapter 1 introduces the research background, problem statement, objectives, challenges, and significance. Chapter 2 reviews related literature on video anomaly detection. Chapter 3 presents the proposed methodology and experimental setup. Chapter 4 discusses experimental results and performance analysis. while Chapter 5 concludes the thesis by summarizing the key contributions.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

Video anomaly detection has become one of the major research topics in the field of computer vision, especially in the surveillance field of automated monitoring. It was one of the first methods that pay attention to weakly supervised ranking schemes and provide anomaly scores to video segments with video-only labels. The techniques also provided massive real-world surveillance with various categories of anomalies, which have become standard in future studies [1].

After that, there were a few loosely supervised approaches that tried to address temporal segment grouping and multiple instances learning to optimize the performance of the anomaly detector in the absence of frame-level annotations. These methods demonstrated that temporal relationships between segments would be carefully designed to have a significant impact on the detection accuracy [5].

Meanwhile, reconstruction-based architecture methods that are not supervised have gained prominence. Convolutional recurrent autoencoders and spatiotemporal autoencoders were suggested to learn to model appearance and motion patterns simultaneously, with high reconstruction error on anomalous events and low error on normal patterns. These techniques were assessed on conventional grounds, proving the necessity of learning spatiotemporal correlations of untrimmed videos that are long [6].

More recent approaches have also used self-supervised learning, with the use of auxiliary proxy tasks to generate meaningful spatiotemporal representations regardless of using explicit annotations of anomaly. Such methods treat deviations of normal behaviour patterns as abnormal in the process of learning normal behaviour patterns by the abundant usage of normal videos. This paradigm was effective in a variety of standard benchmarks that included various types of anomalies and different data sets [7].

The anomaly detection has also been enhanced by memory augmented networks that save the prototypical characteristics of normal events. These models only rebuild the learned normal patterns, and they generate more errors in reconstruction of anomalies. Multi-level memory modules and hybrid memory with reconstruction goals have demonstrated state-of-the-art

performance on a variety of surveillance data sets, as well as proving that memory mechanisms boost discriminative power [8].

Lastly, computational efficiency has become a focus, particularly to be used on edge devices and camera networks on a large scale. Convolutional backbones with lightweight features and effective feature extraction methods have been merged into anomaly detection pipelines to ensure high-accuracy and lower the level of the computational load. More recent progress also investigates masked autoencoder claim structures alongside memory units to learn high-level semantic and spatiotemporal characteristics concomitantly, achieving viable outcomes in the field of actual-world surveillance [9].

2.1 Traditional Approaches to Video Anomaly Detection

Initial studies on video anomaly detection were based on classical methods of computer vision with handcrafted characteristics and statistical analysis. These techniques simulated normal appearance in surveillance shots based on low-level visual information like the movement of objects, object appearance, and pixel changes. Deviations of these pre-established patterns were referred to as anomalies. Although these methods provided a foundation to subsequent studies, they were not amazingly effective in dealing with real, dynamic world-based situations, which curtailed their real-world use [10].

The object-oriented analysis is a typical type of traditional technique. These methods typically began with background modelling to distinguish between moving and non-moving objects in the scene, after which object detection and tracking of moving objects through successive frames were done. Artisanal features such as the size of objects, their shape, distribution colour, and simple motion statistics were extracted and examined to identify abnormal behaviour. The object-based methods were interpretable and computationally efficient, but were extremely sensitive to changes in illumination, background clutters, and occlusions, especially in crowded scenes [11].

Another significant field of study was trajectory-based methods. Objects have been followed through time to produce motion paths, which are defined in terms of velocity, direction, and spatial change. These trajectories were learned to provide normal motion patterns and deviations were detected as anomalies. Although they were useful in irregular motion, they heavily depended on the accurate tracking of objects. Tracking errors were also experienced in crowded or congested environments and minimized reliability. In addition, these techniques

did not pay attention to appearance and context-related information, which restricted the ability to detect semantically interesting anomalies [12].

Complementary to the case of optical flow-based techniques were techniques that operated at the pixel level comparing the motion between two consecutive frames. Motion vectors were identified to calculate features like magnitude and direction and abnormal motion patterns were considered as abnormalities. The optical flow algorithms were also able to capture fine-grained motions but were computationally expensive and prone to noise, camera effects (a moving camera) and lighting variation. This rendered them hard to scale to real time or large-scale surveillance purposes [6].

Irrespective of their input, the traditional methods had several limitations that were inherent. Hand craft effects were not that representational to present spatiotemporal and semantic patterns of real-world videos. They were also sensitive to environmental variation and generally did short term time analysis, they never modelled the long-term dependencies. Their generalizability was further limited by manual parameter tuning and scene specific parameters. These constraints inspired the creation of learning-based solutions that can extract strong features and model temporal variations automatically, which are the basis of the modern deep learning and self-supervised video anomaly detection models which will be discussed further.

2.2 Supervised Learning Approaches

Video anomaly detection supervised learning methods are based upon the explicitly labelled datasets of normal and abnormal events. The anomaly detection in such methods is viewed as a classification or regression problem, so the models are trained to differentiate between the anomalous patterns and the normal behaviour. Initial supervised techniques were encouraging when run in controlled settings but were not scalable or useful in real-world surveillance settings because they required full annotation of their datasets [13].

First supervised approaches used conventional machine learning classifiers that had been trained on manual features that were derived either on a frame-by-frame basis on video or on brief time-scale blocks. Attributes that define motion, appearance and spatiotemporal patterns were handcrafted and loaded into classifiers like support vectors machines, decision trees, or ensemble models. Although such approaches did not perform dismally on small benchmark datasets, they relied heavily on manual feature engineering and parameter optimization.

Further, handcrafted characteristics were unable to generalize across scenes and types of anomalies, which could simplify the subjective semantics of real-world anomalies [10].

Introduction of deep learning made major breakthroughs in supervised video anomaly detection by allowing end-to-end learning of hierarchical representation using raw data. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) were employed to obtain discriminative spatial features of video frames and recurrent neural networks (RNNs), with long short-term memory (LSTM) models obtained temporal dependencies between sequences. Through sharing spatial and temporal patterns, these models performed better than the conventional feature-based models, especially in the complex anomalies where there were changes in appearance and movement simultaneously. The success of deep supervised models, however, was accompanied by a higher computational cost and a high reliance on large amounts of annotated data [4].

This was followed by three-dimensional convolutional neural networks (3D CNNs) where single spatiotemporal volumes are processed rather than processed on a single frame. Using 3D convolutional kernels enabled such models to learn motion and appearance simultaneously to learn short-term temporal dynamics through clips of videos. There was also found to be an improvement in 3D CNNs in terms of feature richness, but it was computationally intensive and needed large-labelled datasets, which were not suitable in terms of long surveillance videos and real-time use [14].

Two-stream architectures were proposed to minimize the computation cost and still retain the accuracy. In such models, a stream receives spatial information in RGB frames, and the other stream receives information on time through optical flow or frame difference. Combination of these streams was complementary information, which improved anomaly detection. Two stream models were more efficient than single-stream, even with better performance, and the additional preprocessing needed to compute motion features, making them inefficient enough to use in edge devices or in real-time applications [15].

Also, temporal aggregation techniques were investigated to deal with long videos during supervision. Videos were broken down into pieces, and features that were sampled across time were pooled together to generate video-level representations. Although this method minimized computational costs it still needed annotated data and could not accurately localize anomalies present in long sequences which reduced frame-level accuracy of the method [5].

Despite these developments, the supervised learning methods have several fundamental shortcomings. First, annotated anomaly information is limited as abnormal occurrence is not common and is costly to label, particularly on a frame-level granularity. The models which are trained on types of anomalies might not detect new or unknown anomaly which will restrict robustness. Extreme class imbalance between normal and abnormal samples tends to bias models to normal behaviour thus lowering the reliability of the detection. Lastly, deep supervised models have high computational requirements making it difficult to implement them in real-time surveillance.

These difficulties have encouraged the movement towards unsupervised and self-supervised paradigms, which seek to acquire the representation of normal behaviour without necessary labelling of anomalies. The functional demand of scalable, efficient, and general-purpose solutions has directly contributed to the design of current anomaly detection systems that adopt pre-trained convolutional networks and self-supervised learning goals, as would be examined in further discussions below as well as in the proposed approach of the present thesis.

2.3 Unsupervised Learning Approaches

Unsupervised learning is now a paradigm in video anomaly detection because there is a dearth of annotated anomaly data in real-world surveillance. Given that anomalous events are uncommon, varied and usually unforeseeable, unmonitored approaches cannot be deployed on large scale bases. Unsupervised methods resolve this by training the patterns of normal behaviour by using normal only data and identifying any deviation as anomalies [8].

Simple unsupervised techniques were based on clustering and statistical modelling of handcrafted features. Normal behaviour was represented by motion descriptors, appearance features and spatiotemporal statistics being extracted and clustered. Things that were outside these clusters were marked as anomalies. Although these techniques decreased reliance on labelled data, they were not efficient with respect to the expressiveness of features that are handcrafted, sensitivity to noise, and environmental variations [16].

Development of deep learning opened the potential of using unsupervised methods that are based on a neural network. Autoencoders were popularized, and they learn to generate normal frames or representations of features. In the inference process, the frames that had high reconstruction errors were considered as anomalous. These approaches enhanced the accuracy

of the detection but tended to over-generalize, which recreated certain unnatural patterns and lowered detection [17].

Recurrent neural net sequence-to-sequence models were proposed to capture the changes over time. These models were trained in the forecasting of future frames based off past sequences. Abnormalities had been identified when the error of prediction was more than the threshold.

These types of models worked well on abnormal motion tasks but failed on long-term dependencies and noise in complex scenes [18].

Generative models also further developed unsupervised anomaly detection. Normal video distributions were modelled with variational Autoencoders and Generative Adversarial Networks. Abnormalities were discovered according to reconstruction probability or quality of generation. Although these methods were expected to give probable information, they were computationally expensive and could not be trained to generate high-resolution or long sequence videos, which limited their actual time use [19].

The other direction aimed at learning the aberrant scores in feature space. The convolutional networks deep embeddings were modelled as distance based or density estimation models, where the test samples that were far away in the normal distribution were considered anomalies. These approaches enhanced robustness compared with pixel level analysis, but still they were not explicitly modelled with time and feature extractors were still heavy [20].

Nevertheless, even with advances, unsupervised approaches have several constraints: most of them need high-capacity models that are not appropriate to resource-constrained systems, assume of no anomalies in training data and are not always capable of distinguishing between rare normal behaviour and actual anomalies semantically. It is difficult to find a balance between reconstruction or prediction accuracy and generalization.

These restrictions have prompted hybrid methods that have involved unsupervised learning with pretrained CNN feature extractors and self-supervised learning with the aim of improving the temporal and contextual knowledge in an efficient manner. The conceptual background of the Efficient-VAD system based on this thesis is such methods.

2.4 Self-Supervised Learning Approaches

Self-supervised learning has also emerged as one of the most popular methods in video anomaly detection, which addresses the limitations of the supervised and unsupervised methods. It is

also not based on manual labelling of anomalous events as is the case with supervised methods. It adds auxiliary tasks to the model to learn meaningful representations, in comparison to the traditional unsupervised techniques. Self-supervised approaches identify spatial and temporal features by exploiting intrinsic properties in video information and thus are applicable in systems with large scale surveillance when there is a lack of or unavailable labelled data [7].

In video anomaly detection, self-supervised learning deals with modelling normal behaviour by using pretext tasks which can be addressed with unlabelled data. Future frame prediction, temporal order checking, motion consistency learning, and the reconstruction-based objectives are common pretext tasks. These activities can be trained to enable the model to memorize the appearance and temporalization patterns. In testing, anomalies are realized when the model cannot do these tasks meaning there is deviation of learned normal behaviour [21].

The strategy of temporal prediction is a popular self-supervised approach. Training Model It is used to predict the future of the frames or feature representation based on previous observations. Convolutional networks are normally used to extract spatial features whereas recurrent or temporal convolutional modules are used to model temporal dependencies. The prediction errors are taken as a measure of anomaly where a high error means anomalous events. Temporal prediction is useful in capturing irregularities in motion and abnormal event sequence, but it can misrepresent over long horizons, and it can be computationally expensive when running directly on raw video frames [22].

This other type of method applies reconstruction-based self-supervised learning with more constraints. In contrast to typical autoencoder models, the methods impose temporal consistency, multi scale reconstruction or feature alignment goals. This discourages trivial reconstruction of anomalies as well as promotes more discriminative learning of normal patterns. These are the methods that enhance robustness compared to simple autoencoders but are also difficult to overcome over-generalization and large computation [11].

Another new method in self-supervised video analysis is contrastive learning. It trains models which generate similar representations of temporally or contextually related pieces of video and isolates unrelated pieces of video. In anomaly detection, this assists in creating small latent representations of normal behaviour and any deviation of these clusters is considered an anomaly. Contrastive learning has benefits of feature discrimination, but must be carefully sampled, and can be computationally intensive due to large batch sizes [23].

Memory-augmented self-supervised models expressly represent normal behaviour through a memory bank of exemplary features. In the process of inference, the received features are matched against the patterns in memory, and anomalies are indicated by the deviation. This increases long term Modelling of normal patterns and decreases over-generalization. But updates and maintenance of memory further complicate and affect the scalability of large surveillance systems [8].

Although the methods have benefits, self-supervised ones have shortcomings. Most of them use elaborate architecture and computationally intensive functions, which restrict the real-time implementation on edge devices. Pretext tasks selection is also especially important and improper designed tasks can result in poor or insignificant representations. There has always been the challenge of balancing the representation of rich features and computational efficiency, particularly when the video stream can be a long one.

Recent studies have thus paid attention to effective self-supervised structures which integrate light CNN feature extractors with temporal learning processes. The pretrained convolutional networks give the network high spatial representations without requiring lots of training, whereas the self-supervised goals present temporal and contextual feedback. This methodology is a compromise between precision, effectiveness, and scalability. With these concepts in mind, the present thesis outlines an effective system of video anomaly detectors that combine both lightweight pretrained CNNs and self-supervised learning techniques, which renders it appropriate to be applied to practice in real-life video surveillance implementation.

2.5 Feature Extraction and Representation Learning

Extraction of features and representation learning are important processes in video anomaly detection since features quality directly influences system accuracy, efficiency, and robustness. High-dimensional raw pixels are in the form of surveillance video, and these are subject to a lot of redundancy and noise. Such data cannot be directly analysed in a computationally expensive and effective way. As such, it is necessary to extract compact and informative features to extract meaningful spatial and temporal patterns as well as minimize computational complexity [24].

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have been trained with specific features which have become popular in extracting features in feature detection; it is able to learn hierarchical representation of features in shapes of objects. Commonly used networks that can be used to

extract spatial features of video frames are networks like VGG, ResNet, and MobileNet. Trained on large-scale datasets of images, these models can learn generic visual representations such as edges, textures, shapes, and semantic structures that can be successfully transferred to downstream tasks of anomaly detection. As fixed feature extractors, the use of pretrained CNNs enables systems to use rich visual representations without the need to undertake large scale task-specific training, which lowers training time, and reduces training requirements based on annotated data [25].

Although deep CNNs have good representational capabilities, they tend to be computationally inefficient and memory-consuming and hence cannot be applied effectively to real-time video processing of resource-limited devices. In this regard, lightweight networks like MobileNet are used or specifically MobileNetV3-Large. To limit the number of parameters and computation cost, these networks use depth-wise separable convolutions but have enough features. MobileNetV3-Large is a trade-off between efficiency and representational capacity and generates small feature embeddings that can be used in real-time video processing in surveillance systems [26].

CNNs are effective at capturing the spatial patterns, but to detect anomalies in videos, Modelling the temporal change of motion and behavioural patterns is necessary. The temporal feature aggregation methods are thus used to process frame-level embeddings to form meaningful temporal features. Conventional methods involve optical flow which quantifies the pixel-level displacement between frames, and frame differencing which quantifies temporal variation in the short time. Although optical flow is computational and detailed in information on motion, it is sensitive to changes in the environment and computationally expensive. Frame differencing is small but does not provide much time context. In more sophisticated types of temporal models, three-dimensional convolutions are employed to learn both spatial and temporal features together. Such approaches can be used to obtain motion patterns, although at a significant computational cost that can limit their use in long video sequences and real-time systems. As an alternative, self-supervised pretext tasks such as solving decoupled spatio-temporal jigsaw puzzles have been proposed to learn discriminative spatial and temporal representations without relying on pre-trained backbones [27].

Temporal aggregation (sliding window) has become a viable approach to compromise between time Modelling and computation. In this scheme frame-level properties are pooled into fixed length temporal windows such that local temporal dynamics can be learned without having to

process entire video streams simultaneously. Sliding windows offer a scalable solution to real-time surveillance and still offer adequate temporal context that can be used to detect anomalies accurately [28].

The quality and the dimensionality of feature embedding are also important factors. High-dimensional features can be used to encode rich information, but these features can also create redundancy and increase memory demands and functions of too small features can be lost. MobileNetV3-Large is a lightweight CNN that can generate moderately sized embeddings (e.g. 960 D), which are found to be effective at containing spatial information without being computationally expensive. These embeddings are compatible with temporal aggregation and anomaly scoring systems, which offer a basis to effective and robust anomaly detection systems.

Stability of the model and learning is further improved through feature normalization and standardization. Normalized features decrease the variations in the scale, enhance the distance-based or reconstruction-based anomaly detectors, and provide the ability to perform consistent evaluation on different segments of video. Good feature representations are needed to distinguish normal behaviour and anomalies, and are the building blocks of deployable, reliable and efficient video anomaly detection systems.

2.6 Memory-Augmented Neural Networks

Video anomaly detection has seen the emergence of memory-augmented neural networks as an important element to overcome the shortcomings of traditional deep networks to model complex and varied normal patterns across extended surveillance videos. The traditional prediction of reconstruction models tends to make overgeneralizations and yield low reconstruction errors even in the case of abnormal events because of their high representational abilities. Memory-based architecture can overcome this by incurring reconstruction or prediction by a small number of learned normal prototiles stored in an external memory module [8].

Features obtained during convolutional encoders in memory-augmented autoencoders are mapped to a memory space, which is a fixed number of slots. The slots represent representative normal patterns, which are only trained on normal training data. In the inference process, the similarity between the input features and memory entries is computed and only highly correlated memory slots are used in the reconstruction process. It is a limited reconstruction

which increases errors on abnormal events which do not correspond to a stored memory representation, increasing the sensitivity to detection [29].

Temporal prediction models have also been augmented with memory. The prototypical motion dynamics are stored in these designs within memory units rather than the fixed appearance features. Sequential models are neuroadaptive models which have interactions with memory, conditioning future frame or feature prediction on pre-learned temporal features. Research indicates that prediction of memory conditions enhances detection of gradual and context-dependent anomalies, that is, especially in crowded scenes with dynamic motion patterns [30].

Memory addressing based on attention has been studied to enhance feature to memory correspondence. Soft attention weights enable discrimination of normal patterns of interest rather than hard assignments, which ensures less sensitivity to noise and variations within classes. Studies indicate that the memory access based on attention results in higher stability in the scores related to anomalies in the long video sequences. To increase the degree of discriminability, certain frameworks put sparsity requirements, whereby only a restricted number of memory slots is activated on a given input [31].

Strategies for updating memories are essential towards reliability. Various works only update the memory during the training so that the prototypes that are stored are only normal patterns. Other methods suggest a regulated online updating by confidence scores or other similarity metrics, which permits a minimal adaptation to changing environments with reduced chances of using abnormal samples. Experiments show that free memory update in inference may deteriorate the performance in detection with time progression [32].

The memory-augmented designs also take into consideration the scalability and efficiency. Compact CNN feature representations are memory-level representations, meaning that they have lower computational overhead than pixel-level processing. By keeping the amount of memory and access rate low it has been demonstrated that detection can be preserved, and real-time inference can be executed on resource-constrained hardware.

In general, memory-augmented neural networks are effective at imposing normality conditions to video anomaly detection. Their integration with off-the-shelf convolutional features, as well as self-supervised learning goals, give them strong Modelling of regular behaviour and less susceptibility to over-generalization, which are a vital part of modern state-of-the-art anomaly detection systems.

2.7 Temporal Modelling and Sequence Learning

Temporal Modelling of video anomaly detection is a vital component of the technology since surveillance video is sequential. Abnormal events tend to be in the form of abnormal dynamics of motion or time variations and cannot be represented by studying single frames. Consequently, sequence learning methods have been widely studied to capture short term changes in motions and long-term time-dependent dependencies [33].

In the initial approaches, recurrent neural networks were used to represent temporal dependencies on features produced by convolutional encoders, that is, LSTMs and GRUs. They were tested on standard data sets such as UCSD Pedestrian and CUHK Avenue. Findings established that temporal prediction errors might be more effective in detecting abnormal events than frame-level-reconstruction. Nevertheless, recurrent models had difficulty of long-range dependencies and overlapping patterns of movement, leading to the creation of hierarchical or multi-scale temporal structures [34].

Hierarchical temporal models break down the video sequences into several scales to model both fine-grained motions and larger patterns of motion. It has been shown that at multi-scales, the representations are better able to detect fine anomalies like slow or abnormal pedestrian motion, which is not easily detected by single-scale models. Dilated and causal convolutions have also been used to model sequential patterns using Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCNs). TCNs are parallelized and more stable and can train faster as compared to recurrent architecture and are competitive in terms of anomaly detection performance [35].

Predictive temporal structures have become popular, where the future frame or feature embeddings are modelled based on the previous observations. In normal motion, the predictions closely match the real findings; any deviation leads to high prediction errors indicating anomalies. On datasets like the Shanghai Tech Campus, it can be assessed that prediction-based temporal models perform better compared to reconstruction-only temporal models, especially on sudden or more complicated motion anomalies [36].

Temporal goals are frequently self-supervised and are used to further refine feature representations whilst not using labelled anomalies. Temporal order verification, future feature prediction, and motion consistency learning tasks are pretext activities that are implemented to direct models to learn discriminative temporal patterns. This improves the detection of slow

and context-sensitive anomalies, which are resistant to a wide range of surveillance conditions [5].

Temporal Modelling has been enhanced with attention mechanisms to enhance localization of anomalies. Temporal attention gives various weight to the frames or clips based on their relevance in learning that is concerned with normal patterns. It is mentioned that attention-based models increase accuracy in detection of anomalous parts, particularly in long and uncut videos with fluctuating motion patterns [37]. Temporal models are further stabilized by memory-augmented networks that are hybrid designs that combine temporal Modelling with the use of anomaly scoring to match sequential predictions with prototypical normal patterns in memory.

Another important consideration in the temporal Modelling is efficiency. It is observed that the sensibility to temporal anomalies can be maintained by operating temporal modules on small CNN features at lower computational costs. These designs are especially applicable in real-time surveillance systems, in which long-term video processing needs to trade accuracy and efficiency.

2.8 Threshold Selection and Decision Boundaries

Video anomaly detection frameworks require threshold selection and decision boundary formulation in the process since it is used to establish how continuous anomaly scores are transformed into discrete anomaly detections. The reconstruction error, prediction error, or feature-to-memory similarities tend to acquire anomaly scores. It is a well-known fact in literature that inadequately selected thresholds may obscure genuine anomalies or create a very high number of false positives of interest, particularly in dynamic surveillance contexts [38].

Most of the studies use global thresholds obtained after the statistical distribution of anomaly scores on normal training data. Percentile thresholds such as those of percentiles, put samples above a particular quantile of the normal score distribution as anomalous. Tests on datasets such as the UCSD Pedestrian and CUHK Avenue demonstrate that the percentile thresholds are a simple and efficient way of separating normal and abnormal events. Nevertheless, they can be weak in multi-scene datasets in which motion patterns can be different at different locations. To address this, memory-augmented approaches have introduced prototypical normal patterns with a test-time update scheme that dynamically adapts to unseen scenes, reducing the need for a single global threshold [39].

Adaptive thresholding has also been developed with respect to scene variability. These techniques will modify thresholds using either local score distributions, time windows, or motion statistics. Studies have shown that adaptive thresholds minimize false alarms in crowded or moving scenes as well as enhancing short-duration anomalies. Before thresholding, sliding window and temporal smoothing methods are commonly used on the scores of anomalies to stabilize the scores. More recent approaches replace large memory banks with a lightweight Dynamic Prototype Unit that encodes normal patterns in real time, providing a memory-efficient alternative for scoring anomalous frames [40].

Another method is the use of probabilistic and likelihood-based thresholds. Normal anomaly score distributions are modelled by Gaussian, mixture or any other probabilistic model and decision limits are obtained by using confidence intervals or likelihood ratios. It is reported that probabilistic thresholds are more robust to noise and intra-class variation than fixed or heuristic thresholds, such as on large-scale datasets, such as ShanghaiTech Campus and UCFCrime[41].

The learnable thresholds that can be part of the anomaly detection pipeline are also discussed in recent works. These thresholds are automatically modified by making use of margin-based optimization or decision-layer optimization in training. The comparison findings show that learned thresholds are adaptable to challenging surveillance conditions and enhance this detection with fragile normal behaviours and various camera perspectives [42].

Detection of thresholds in self-supervised or loosely supervised schemes is commonly done by optimization or clustering of normal scores of anomalies. Clustering Techniques like k-means clustering, density estimation or percentile separation have been shown to be able to find natural boundaries in the score space without need of annotated anomalies. The methods increase cross-dataset generalization and decrease the use of manually specified thresholds [43].

The other important factor when selecting the threshold is efficiency. Simpler statistical computations, sliding-window adaptive thresholds, or probabilistic confidence intervals are desirable to be deployed in real-time because of their lightweight. These are detection responsive and process continuous video streams without introducing extra computation.

2.9 Datasets and Benchmarks

Video anomaly detection method evaluation is also based on a limited number of publicly available surveillance datasets that are a standard benchmark in literature. The datasets are

meant to mirror the real surveillance challenges in the world where anomalies are challenging to come by, they are diverse and context dependent. Majority of benchmarks are based on unsupervised or loosely supervised guidelines, and most of them are annotated with an objective of evaluation rather than training [41].

One of the most often used and the first one is the UCSD Pedestrian dataset. It includes surveillance tapes that were taken by inanimate cameras that were placed on pedestrian walkways. Anomalies involve bicycles, vehicles, and odd movements of pedestrians. The dataset is also of high performance when it comes to early reconstruction-based and prediction-based methods, but its simple scenes and lack of diversity in anomalies are not a complete simulation of the real-world surveillance complexities [44].

CUHK Avenue data presents more difficult conditions, such as running, throwing objects, and other abnormal human behaviours in a campus setting. Frame based annotation allows fine temporal analysis. It is found in literature that Avenue is tougher than UCSD, as motion patterns and camera perspective are varied and, therefore, it can be used to test temporal modelling and memory-based approaches [11].

The ShanghaiTech Campus data contributes to benchmark complexity in a great way. It contains videos of many cameras, which record a large number of anomalies, such as the crowd abnormalities, and the unusual interactions of objects. Its multi-scene quality poses a challenge to the deep learning frameworks because it requires a generalization capability and challenges strategies that make assumptions about the scene [5].

The UCF-Crime data is concerned with actual crimes in diverse settings. They, unlike frame level data sets, offer video level annotations rendering it appropriate to weakly supervised learning. The noise and temporal ambiguity caused by the size of the dataset and the variety of events put a premium on the robustness and not on the localization of the event. In literature, it has been identified to play a significant role in assessing large scale, practical anomaly detection systems [1].

The XD-Violence dataset also paves the way to the long and unedited videos with visual modalities and audio modalities. Categorical violent activities involve time-based thinking and discrimination are attributes to identifying them successfully. Although useful in investigating the long-duration anomaly detection, the dataset used is not generalizable in the whole surveillance scenario due to its concentration in violence [16].

Subway surveillance datasets are other smaller datasets that take note of abnormalities such as fare evasion or unlawful access. These data sets are useful in assessing the temporal regularity, threshold methodologies as well as high-resolution anomaly detection since they have limited environments [45].

This paper discusses benchmark protocols in which models are trained using normal-only data and anomaly scores are evaluated based on entire video scores. Frame sampling, smoothing of time and aggregation of scores is standardized to make comparisons fair. It is always reported in literature that model performance differs across data sets, which makes it necessary to evaluate models on multi datasets.

Recent papers also note limitations in the existing standards including subjectivity of annotations, bias in the dataset and limited diversity of anomalies. These problems have inspired methods of studying more generalizable models with pretrained CNNs, self-supervised learning and cross-dataset evaluation to make less reliance on data-specific patterns.

2.10 Real-Time and Efficient Systems

Operational characteristics of video anomaly detection system need real-time processing and computational efficiency to be implemented in the real world. Literature reveals that the computational cost is primarily determined by three factors namely feature extraction, temporal modelling, and memory- or prediction-based scoring. Researchers have produced methods of maximizing each of the components without compromising the detection accuracy [1].

Pre-trained convolutional neural networks are extensively used to feature-extract to decrease computation. Research gives results that processing with high-level CNN feature embeddings, rather than raw pixels, reduces the processing requirements significantly. Inference speed and a quality of the representation. CNN architectures that are lightweight (or truncated feature layers) trade-off between speed and the quality of the representation. Tests on data sets such as UCSD Pedestrian and ShanghaiTech Campus indicate that at the feature level, optimization can lead to a significant reduction of processing time without causing significant decrease in detection performance [25].

Another significant source of computational burden is said to be temporal modelling, particularly in recurrent or predictive structures. Hierarchical temporal models and temporal convolutional networks (TCNs) provide a successful alternative to long-sequence recurrent networks where computation among the frames or clips can be performed in parallel.

Multiscale temporal aggregation and dilated convolutions represent the long-range dependencies with minimal latency, and therefore they are both useful when dealing with streaming surveillance inputs [5].

Memory-augmented architectures enhance the discrimination of anomalies but cause computational overhead of accessing the memory. This is solved through research by limiting the size of the memory, using sparsity constraints, and working with memory modules integrated with low-dimensional CNN features. Empirical findings indicate that these optimizations preserve the discriminative capacity of memory with the capacity of inferring almost in real-time to regular GPUs and CPUs [8].

Anomaly scoring and thresholding are also important. Computation of sliding-window scores, adaptive thresholds and probabilistic confidence-based decision machines are chosen in favour of real time evaluation. These methods do not make any complex calculations on the whole video sequences. The benchmarks show that a good combination of low weight scoring, optimized features, and temporal modules compares to a fair balance between accuracy and speed.

Lastly, hybrid design, which incorporates pre-trained CNNs, temporal modules, and memory-augmented networks are claimed to be useful in real-time applications. It can detect anomalies at frame rates that are compatible with the output of surveillance cameras by using architectural optimizations, including using compressed feature embeddings, limited memory access, and parallelization of temporal computations. Cross-dataset tests affirm such systems are sound even in case of high-motion or multi-camera.

2.11 Comparison of State-of-the-Art Methods

Table 2.1 offers a side-by-side comparison of state-of-the-art video anomaly detection techniques. It outlines the type of learning of each method, the strategy of feature extraction, benchmark datasets, limitations, and their reported performance (AUC/ accuracy). The given comparison identifies the advantages and disadvantages of different methods and creates a clear vision of the existing trends in the research on video anomaly detection.

Table 2.1: Literature review summary of anomaly detection methods in surveillance videos.

#Ref	Authors & Year	Methodology	Learning Type	Feature Extraction	Datasets	Limitations	Results (AUC)
[1]	Sultani et al., 2018	MIL ranking framework	Weakly Supervised	C3D + motion features	UCF-Crime	Limited temporal modelling	UCF-Crime: 75.41
[7]	Georgescu et al., 2020/21	Self-Supervised + Multi-Task	Self-Supervised	3D CNN + object detector	Avenue, Shanghai Tech, UCSD Ped2	Proxy tasks may not generalize	Avenue: 92.8, ShanghaiTech: 90.2, Ped2: 99
[16]	Zaheer et al., 2022	Clustering-Aided Weak Supervision	Weakly Supervised	ResNet50	UCF-Crime, Shanghai Tech, UCSD Ped2	Sensitive to cluster noise	UCF-Crime: 84.1, ShanghaiTech: 91.46, UCSD Ped2: 95.79
[39]	Park et al., 2020	Memory-guided normality with memory module & update scheme	Self-Supervised / Unsupervised	2D Conv-AE (U-Net) with memory (10 items \times 512)	UCSD Ped2, CUHK Avenue, Shanghai Tech	Memory diversity depends on compactness/separateness losses	Ped2: 97.0, Avenue: 88.5, ShanghaiTech: 70.5
[40]	Lv et al., 2021	Meta-Prototype Network with Dynamic Prototype Unit (DPU)	Unsupervised / Meta-learned	Auto-encoder + attention-based prototype pool	UCSD Ped1/Ped2, CUHK Avenue, Shanghai Tech	Limited prototype quantity; degrades with too many prototypes	Ped2: 96.9, Avenue: 89.5, ShanghaiTech: 73.8

[46]	Liu et al., 2021	Hybrid flow reconstruction + flow-guided frame prediction (ML-MemAE-SC + CVAE)	Unsupervised	Multi-level memory autoencoder with skip connections	UCSD Ped2, CUHK Avenue, Shanghai Tech	~10 FPS inference; requires optical flow preprocessing	Ped2: 99.3, Avenue: 91.1, ShanghaiTech: 76.2
[47]	Yu et al., 2020	Video Event Completion via visual cloze test (patch erasure)	Self-Supervised	U-Net over spatio-temporal cubes + optical flow	UCSD Ped2, CUHK Avenue, Shanghai Tech	Relies on pre-trained object detector for cube extraction	Ped2: 97.3, Avenue: 89.6, ShanghaiTech: 74.8
[48]	Wu et al., 2022	Self-Supervised Sparse Representation (S3R) with en-Normal / de-Normal modules	Self-Supervised / Unsupervised	Pre-trained I3D + learned dictionary	Shanghai Tech, UCF-Crime, XD-Violence	Dictionary quality depends on training set coverage	ShanghaiTech: 79.89, UCF-Crime: 77.15
[49]	Pang et al., 2020	Self-trained Deep Ordinal Regression (end-to-end)	Unsupervised / Self-trained	Pre-trained ResNet-50 + FC scoring head	UCSD Ped1/Ped2, Subway, UMN	Initial pseudo-labels quality bounds final performance	UCSD Ped2: 83.2, Subway Entrance: 88.1, UMN All: 97.4
[50]	Ristea et al., 2022	Self-Supervised Predictive Convolutional Attentive Block (SSPCAB) integrated into base models	Self-Supervised (block)	Masked dilated convolution + channel attention	MVTec AD, CUHK Avenue, Shanghai Tech	Architectural block only; requires host model	Avenue: 92.9, ShanghaiTech: 83.6 (integrated into Georgescu et al.)
[27]	Wang et al., 2022	Decoupled spatio-temporal jigsaw puzzle	Self-Supervised	3D CNN (no pre-trained backbone) on object-	UCSD Ped2, CUHK Avenue,	Depends on YOLOv3 object detector	Ped2: 99.0, Avenue: 92.2, ShanghaiTech: 84.3

		solving (multi-label)		centric cubes	Shanghai Tech		
[3]	Nayak & Chaudhari, 2023	Pseudo-label generation + MIL	Weakly Supervised	C3D / I3D spatial-temporal features	UCF-Crime, Shanghai Tech	Noisy labels	UCF-Crime: 84.6, ShanghaiTech: 92.3
[45]	Tian et al., 2021	Temporal feature magnitude + MIL	Weakly Supervised	I3D features	UCF-Crime, Shanghai Tech	Magnitude assumption may fail	ShanghaiTech: 97.2, UCF-Crime: 84.3
Our	This Thesis, 2023	Memory augmented LSTM Autoencoder	Self-Supervised	Pretrained MobileNet V3-Large	UCF-Crime	May struggle with extremely subtle anomalies	AUC: 98.61

2.12 Research Gaps and Limitations Identified in Existing Work

Although video anomaly detection has achieved considerable advancement, there are still some essential research gaps and limitations in literature. Restricted time-modelling is one of the significant shortcomings that have been experienced in most approaches. Various methods, especially the initial and loosely supervised methods, are based on short and weakly-supervised features and fail to sufficiently reflect the long-term dependencies in a complex surveillance setting. This weakness makes it less sensitive to anomalies that are slowly growing or need a longer time frame to be identified. The techniques that depend on time aggregation and not on learning a sequence properly tend to miss the detection of small or situation-driven abnormal behaviours [1].

Although the methods with weak supervision are feasible when dealing with big datasets, they rely heavily on video-level labels. These labels are usually noisy, unclear, or inconsistent, minimizing the accuracy of localizing anomalies. Currently sophisticated frameworks including temporal attention or instance selection are also vulnerable to errors caused by uncertain labels. Equally, self-supervised methods are based on pretext tasks or auxiliary goals to direct representation learning. Nevertheless, when the pretext tasks are not tightly related to the semantic nature of anomalies, the learned features are not necessarily the best to be used in

the detection of anomalies in the real world, leading to low detection rates, particularly in natural and unpredictable surveillance environments [7].

The use of pre-trained CNN backbones to extract features is becoming common to take advantage of hierarchical spatial representations. Though these networks offer strong frame level functions, they might fail to detect fine motion dynamics, object interaction, or other environmental contextual abnormalities that are important in detecting subtle anomalies. More successful approaches include high-performing methods which use transformers, multi-scale feature fusion or vision-language alignment that are more accurate but high-computation, high memory, and long-latency inference. This is so computationally intensive that the practical applications of these models to real-time surveillance are restricted, especially in edge devices or a multi-network of cameras.

The other limitation that needs to be persistent is the benchmarking datasets. Popular datasets, including UCF-Crime, ShanghaiTech Campus, CUHK Avenue, UCSD Pedestrian and XD-Violence, though typical in the literature, are limited in diversity in terms of type of anomaly, changes in environment, and camera position. The scarcity of various real-life conditions limits the generalization ability of trained models, and it is not easy to test the performance of approaches in observed or new anomalies. Furthermore, other datasets offer video level annotations only, thus hindering fine frame-level scoring and creation of fine-grained localization procedures.

Lastly, efficiency and scalability are also a challenge. Numerous state-of-the-art algorithms are exactly accurate in detection but need either a large amount of computation, a long processing time, or a large memory footprint. This renders them inappropriate to be used in real-time application of continuous monitoring. The balancing of accuracy, efficiency and robustness remains an open issue in the research on video anomaly detection.

To address these gaps, the methodology proposed in this thesis aims at efficient, robust, and scalable anomaly detection. With the combination of pre-trained lightweight CNNs that extract spatial features and self-supervised learning with memory augmented LSTM modules improve the consistency of memory and limit reconstruction on the normal patterns to be learned, which solves the over-generalization issue. The method is a direct response to the weaknesses of the current literature, which provides a working surveillance system based on accuracy, robustness, and efficiency.

Chapter 3

Materials and Methods

This chapter presents a comprehensive description of the materials, methodologies, and experimental procedures employed in the development of the Efficient-VAD system for video anomaly detection. The chapter is organized into several key sections: dataset description, system architecture, feature extraction methodology, model architecture and design, training procedures, inference pipeline, evaluation methodology, and experimental setup. Each section provides detailed technical specifications to ensure reproducibility and clarity of the proposed approach.

3.1 Dataset

3.1.1 Dataset Selection

The UCF-Crime dataset is selected as it provides large-scale, real-world surveillance videos and is widely used as a benchmark for video anomaly detection. Its structure supports self supervised learning by allowing training exclusively on normal videos while enabling frame level evaluation during testing.

3.1.2 Dataset Description

UCF-Crime consists of long, untrimmed surveillance videos captured from diverse real-world environments such as public areas, traffic scenes, and security installations.

- **Training Set:** Contains only normal videos and is used to learn normal spatiotemporal behaviour patterns without anomaly labels.
- **Test Set:** Includes normal videos and anomalous videos from 13 classes: Abuse, Arrest, Arson, Assault, Burglary, Explosion, Fighting, Road Accidents, Robbery, Shooting, Shoplifting, Stealing, and Vandalism.
- **Annotations:** Frame-level ground labels are provided for evaluation only.

3.1.3 Dataset Preprocessing

All videos are processed using a fixed preprocessing pipeline. Videos are decoded using OpenCV, and frames are sampled with a constant stride to reduce redundancy. Frames are resized to 224×224 pixels and normalized using ImageNet statistics. Spatial features are

extracted using MobileNetV3-Large and stored as NumPy (.npy) files to improve training and inference efficiency.

3.1.4 Data Splitting Strategy

The dataset is divided into two non-overlapping subsets. The training subset contains only 131 normal videos, while the testing subset includes both 131 normal and 950 anomalous videos. This strict separation ensures compliance with the self-supervised learning paradigm and prevents anomaly information leakage during training.

3.2 System Architecture Overview

The proposed Efficient-VAD system is designed as a lightweight and modular pipeline for real-time video anomaly detection. The architecture consists of three core stages: spatial feature extraction, temporal anomaly modelling, and anomaly scoring.

Raw input videos are first processed by a pretrained MobileNetV3-Large network to extract compact frame-level spatial features. These features are then organized into fixed-length temporal sequences and passed to a memory-augmented LSTM autoencoder. The temporal model learns normal motion and appearance dynamics using only normal data.

An external memory module constrains the latent representations to normal behaviour patterns, increasing reconstruction error for anomalous events. During inference, reconstruction errors are computed and mapped to frame-level anomaly scores. A threshold-based decision mechanism is applied to identify abnormal segments.

This modular design ensures computational efficiency, scalability, and suitability for real-time surveillance deployment.

Figure 3.1: System architecture of the proposed Efficient-VAD system

This diagram 3.1 illustrates the main architecture of Efficient-VAD. Input video frames are processed by a pretrained MobileNetV3-Large network to extract efficient spatial features, which are then passed to a memory-augmented LSTM autoencoder that models normal behaviour and highlights anomalies through reconstruction error.

3.3 Feature Extraction Methodology

3.3.1 Feature Extractor Selection

MobileNetV3-Large is used as the spatial feature extractor due to its lightweight architecture and high efficiency. The model provides a good trade-off between representational capacity and computational cost, making it suitable for real-time video anomaly detection on resource constrained systems.

3.3.2 Feature Extraction Process

Each video frame is resized to 224×224 pixels and normalized using ImageNet statistics before being passed through the pretrained MobileNetV3-Large network. The final classification layers are removed, and features are extracted from the last convolutional block.

Global average pooling is applied to obtain a fixed-length feature vector of 960 dimensions per frame. Features are extracted in batches and stored as NumPy (.npy) files to avoid redundant computation during training and inference.

3.3.3 Feature Consistency and Validation

Features are validated to ensure correct dimensions ($N \text{ frames} \times 960 \text{ features}$). Mean and standard deviation of features are computed for quality assessment. Any corrupted or incomplete feature files are automatically discarded or regenerated to maintain consistency across the dataset.

3.4 Model Architecture

The proposed Efficient-VAD model is a memory-augmented LSTM autoencoder developed for self-supervised video anomaly detection. The model is designed to learn normal spatial temporal patterns from feature sequences extracted from surveillance videos and to identify anomalies through reconstruction errors. The overall architecture is composed of three main components:

1. Encoder, which compresses high-dimensional input features into a compact temporal latent representation.
2. Memory Module, which stores representative prototypes of normal behaviour and constrains the reconstruction process.
3. Decoder, which reconstructs the original feature sequences from the memory-enhanced latent representation.

This architectural design ensures that only normal patterns observed during training can be accurately reconstructed.

Training Flow (Self-Supervised, Normal Only)

Figure 3.2: Self-Supervised Training Flow Using Normal Data

This diagram 3.2 presents the self-supervised training process of the proposed system. The model is trained only on normal video sequences, allowing the memory module to learn normal patterns so that abnormal events can be detected during testing without requiring labelled anomaly data.

3.4.1 Encoder

The encoder processes sequences of frame-level features and transforms them into a lowdimensional latent space while preserving temporal dependencies.

The input to the encoder is a sequence of feature vectors with dimensions $B \times S \times 960$, where B denotes the batch size and S represents the sequence length. In this work, each sequence consists of 10 consecutive frames.

Initially, a fully connected layer projects the input features from 960 to 256 dimensions. This projection is followed by a ReLU activation function to introduce non-linearity and a dropout layer with a rate of 0.2 to reduce overfitting.

The projected features are then passed through a single-layer LSTM network with a hidden size of 64. The LSTM is configured in batch-first mode to enable efficient batch processing. The encoder outputs a latent representation of size $B \times S \times 64$, which captures compact temporal patterns present in normal video sequences.

3.4.2 Memory Module

The memory module plays a central role in restricting the reconstruction capability of the model to learned normal patterns. It maintains a set of learnable memory slots, each representing a prototype of normal behaviour.

The memory is implemented as a learnable matrix $M \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d}$, where N is the number of memory slots and d is the latent dimension. In the proposed model, 50 memory slots are used, each with a dimensionality of 64. The memory matrix is initialized using a uniform distribution with a standard deviation of $1/\sqrt{N}$.

To access the memory, the latent representation produced by the encoder is first flattened across the batch and temporal dimensions, resulting in $z_{flat} \in \mathbb{R}^{(B \times S) \times d}$. Attention weights are then computed using a SoftMax operation over the similarity between the latent vectors and the memory slots:

$$a = \text{softmax}(z_{flat} \cdot M^T) \dots\dots\dots 1$$

These attention measures determine the relevance of each memory slot for the given input. The memory-augmented latent representation is obtained through a weighted sum of the memory slots:

$$z_{flat}^{\hat{}} = a \cdot M \dots\dots\dots 2$$

The resulting representation is reshaped back to $\hat{z} \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times S \times d}$ and forwarded to the decoder.

To ensure selective and discriminative memory access, entropy-based regularization is applied to encourage sharp attention distributions, while sparsity constraints promote the activation of only a limited number of memory slots for each input sequence.

3.4.3 Decoder

The decoder reconstructs the original feature sequences from the memory-enhanced latent representation. It mirrors the encoder structure in reverse order.

The decoder consists of a single-layer LSTM with an input size of 64 and a hidden size of 256. This LSTM processes the memory-constrained latent sequences and outputs a temporal representation of size $B \times S \times 256$.

A fully connected layer then maps the LSTM output back to the original feature dimension of 960, producing reconstructed feature sequences of size $B \times S \times 960$. These reconstructed features are used to compute reconstruction errors during training and inference.

3.4.4 Complete Forward Pass

The forward propagation of the Efficient-VAD model follows these steps:

1. The input feature sequence $X \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times S \times 960}$ is projected to 256 dimensions using a fully connected layer.
2. The projected features are processed by the encoder LSTM to obtain a latent representation $Z \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times S \times 64}$.
3. The latent representation is flattened and passed through the memory module to compute attention weights and retrieve memory-constrained features.
4. The memory-enhanced latent representation is reshaped and forwarded to the decoder LSTM.
5. The decoder reconstructs the input features, producing $\hat{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times S \times 960}$, along with the corresponding attention weights.

The reconstruction error between X and \hat{X} serves as the primary indicator for anomaly detection.

3.4.5 Hyperparameters

- Input dimension: 960
- Encoder/decoder hidden dimension: 256
- Latent dimension: 64

- Number of memory slots: 50
- Sequence length: 10 frames.

3.5 Training Methodology

The objective of training is to learn a compact representation of normal spatial-temporal patterns such that the proposed model can accurately reconstruct feature sequences corresponding to normal activities while failing to reconstruct anomalous patterns. Since the training data contains only normal samples, the learning process follows a self-supervised paradigm. Anomalies are identified during inference through elevated reconstruction errors resulting from the inability of the model to represent unseen abnormal patterns.

This objective is achieved by optimizing a composite loss function that combines reconstruction accuracy with memory-related regularization terms.

3.5.1 Loss Functions

The total training loss consists of three components: reconstruction loss, entropy regularization loss, and memory sparsity loss. These losses jointly guide the model towards learning discriminative and compact normal behaviour representations.

3.5.1.1 Reconstruction Loss

The reconstruction loss quantifies the difference between the input feature sequences and their reconstructed counterparts produced by the decoder. Mean Squared Error (MSE) is used to penalize reconstruction discrepancies across all temporal and feature dimensions:

$$L_{rec} = \frac{1}{B \times S \times D} \sum_{i=1}^B \sum_{k=1}^S \sum_{j=1}^D (X_{ijk} - \hat{X}_{ijk})^2 \dots \dots \dots 3$$

where B denotes the batch size, S is the sequence length, and D represents the feature dimension (960). Minimising this loss encourages the model to accurately reconstruct normal feature patterns observed during training.

3.5.1.2 Entropy Loss

Entropy loss is introduced to regulate the attention distribution over memory slots. It discourages uniform memory access and promotes confident selection of a limited number of memory prototypes. The entropy loss is defined as:

$$= -\frac{1}{B \times S} \sum^{B \times S \times N}$$

$$L_{ent} = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M a_{ij} \log(a_{ij} + \epsilon) \dots \dots \dots 4$$

where a_{ij} denotes the attention weight assigned to the j^{th} memory slot for the i^{th} latent vector, N is the number of memory slots, and ϵ is a small constant to ensure numerical stability. Lower entropy values indicate sharper attention distributions, which improves the discrimination of normal patterns.

3.5.1.3 Memory Sparsity Loss

To further enforce selective memory utilization, an L1-based sparsity loss is applied to the attention weights:

$$L_{sparse} = \frac{1}{B \times S} \sum_{i=1}^{B \times S} \sum_{j=1}^N |a_{ij}| \dots \dots \dots 5$$

This term encourages sparse attention vectors, ensuring that only a small subset of memory slots is activated for each input sequence. Such sparsity strengthens the representation of normal behaviour and limits the reconstruction capacity for anomalous inputs.

3.5.1.4 Total Loss Function

The overall training objective is defined as a weighted sum of the three loss components:

$$L_{total} = L_{rec} + \lambda_{ent} L_{ent} + \lambda_{sparse} L_{sparse} \dots \dots \dots 6$$

where $\lambda_{ent} = 0.0002$ and $\lambda_{sparse} = 0.001$ control the influence of entropy and sparsity regularisation, respectively. These weights balance reconstruction fidelity with memory selectivity.

3.5.2 Training Procedure

The training process follows a structured and reproducible workflow.

Initially, all feature files corresponding to normal training videos are loaded from the designated directory. Sliding windows of fixed temporal length are generated from each feature sequence, with overlapping windows created using a predefined stride. These windows are shuffled to ensure randomness during training.

The Efficient-VAD model is then initialized with the selected architectural hyperparameters. The memory matrix is initialized using a uniform distribution, and the model is transferred to the available computational device.

Training is performed using the Adam optimizer with a fixed learning rate. During each training epoch, batches of sliding windows are forwarded through the network to compute reconstructed features and memory attention weights. The total loss is calculated, gradients are backpropagated, and model parameters are updated accordingly. Training metrics, including reconstruction and regularization losses, are monitored throughout the process.

Upon completion of training, the learned model parameters are saved for subsequent inference.

3.5.3 Training Hyperparameters

The training configuration is summarized below:

Table 3.1: Training Hyperparameters of the Efficient-VAD Model

Parameter	Value
Batch size	128
Number of epochs	30
Learning rate	0.0002
Sequence length	10
Sliding window stride	5
Entropy loss weight	0.0002
Sparsity loss weight	0.001

These values were empirically selected to ensure stable optimization and reliable convergence.

3.5.4 Training Implementation Details

The training process is implemented in the script `scripts/2_train.py`. A custom dataset class is used to efficiently load feature files and generate sliding windows on-the-fly. The implementation includes integrated loss computation, real-time progress tracking, and exception handling to manage missing or corrupted data. This design ensures both computational efficiency and robustness during large-scale training.

3.6 Inference Pipeline

The inference stage evaluates unseen videos by quantifying deviations from learned normal reconstruction behaviour. The process is fully unsupervised and computes anomaly scores using reconstruction error and memory attention statistics without requiring anomaly labels.

3.6.1 Feature Loading and Preprocessing

Test features are loaded from disk with recursive directory support. Each file is verified for dimensional correctness ($N \times 960$), and invalid or insufficient sequences are discarded. Frame indices are reconstructed based on the frame sampling configuration to preserve temporal correspondence between scores and original videos.

3.6.2 Window-Based Inference

The trained Efficient-VAD model is restored from checkpoint and executed in evaluation mode. Feature sequences are segmented into overlapping temporal windows of fixed length using a sliding window strategy. Windows are processed in batches to improve runtime efficiency.

For each window, the model reconstructs the input features, and reconstruction error is computed as the mean squared difference between original and reconstructed features:

$$E = \frac{1}{S \cdot D} \sum (X - \hat{X})^2 \dots \dots \dots 7$$

The resulting values represent window-level anomaly scores.

3.6.3 Temporal Score Aggregation

Window-level errors are projected back to frame-level scores by assigning each window score to its temporal centre. Overlapping windows are merged using linear interpolation. To suppress high-frequency noise, Gaussian smoothing is applied with a fixed kernel size. Memory attention entropy is computed in parallel and used as an auxiliary abnormality signal.

3.6.4 Decision Strategy

Frame-level anomaly scores are threshold using a percentile-based rule and Otsu's, where the threshold is defined as the 98th percentile of all scores within a video or if the results are incorrect then we used the Otsu's suggested threshold. Frames exceeding the threshold are labelled anomalous. Video-level decisions are derived using maximum score aggregation to retain sensitivity to brief abnormal events.

3.6.5 Output Artifacts

For each video, the pipeline produces serialized outputs containing frame-level anomaly scores, window-level errors, attention entropy values, and reconstructed frame indices. A summary file aggregates per-video statistics and final predictions for evaluation and reporting.

3.6.6 Inference Configuration

Inference parameters match the training setup to maintain consistency. The sequence length is set to 10 frames with a stride of 5. Batch size is selected based on available hardware. Gaussian smoothing uses a kernel size of 5, and percentile-based thresholding is enabled by default.

3.7 Evaluation Methodology

This section describes the quantitative and computational evaluation strategy adopted to assess the performance and efficiency of the proposed Efficient-VAD framework on surveillance video anomaly detection.

3.7.1 Evaluation Metrics

Performance evaluation is carried out primarily at the video level, using anomaly scores generated during inference. Both threshold-independent and threshold-dependent metrics are reported.

The principal metric is the Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUCROC), which measures the model’s ability to rank anomalous videos higher than normal ones across all decision thresholds. AUC-ROC is computed using continuous video-level anomaly scores without binarization.

For threshold-based analysis, standard binary classification metrics are computed. Accuracy measures overall prediction correctness and is defined as:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \dots\dots\dots 8$$

where TP , TN , FP , and FN represent true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives, respectively.

Precision quantifies the reliability of anomaly predictions and is computed as:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \dots\dots\dots 9$$

Recall (sensitivity) measures the proportion of actual anomalous videos correctly detected:

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \dots\dots\dots 10$$

To provide a balanced evaluation under class imbalance, the F1-score is calculated as the harmonic mean of precision and recall:

$$\text{F1-Score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \dots\dots\dots 11$$

A confusion matrix is also generated to explicitly analyze misclassification patterns across normal and anomalous categories.

3.7.2 Evaluation Procedure

Evaluation is performed using aggregated inference outputs stored in results/inference/inference_summary.csv. This file contains per-video maximum anomaly scores, average scores, entropy values, and predicted labels.

Ground truth labels are automatically derived from the dataset directory structure, where abnormal event categories are treated as anomalous and normal videos as non-anomalous.

The evaluation pipeline computes the ROC curve and corresponding AUC score using continuous anomaly scores. An optimal decision threshold is selected using Youden’s J statistic, which maximizes the difference between true positive rate and false positive rate. Binary predictions are then generated at this threshold to compute accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and the confusion matrix.

3.7.3 Visual and Diagnostic Analysis

To support detailed performance analysis, multiple visualizations are generated. These include ROC curves, precision-recall curves, score distribution histograms, and confusion matrix heatmaps. In addition, frame-level anomaly score timelines are plotted for selected videos with ground truth annotations to examine temporal localization behaviour. A t-SNE projection of anomaly scores is also produced to analyse score separability between normal and anomalous samples.

All visual outputs are saved as high-resolution figures for inclusion in the thesis.

3.7.4 Efficiency Evaluation

Beyond detection accuracy, computational efficiency is explicitly evaluated to assess deployment feasibility. The efficiency analysis reports per-video inference time, effective processing speed in frames per second, peak memory usage, and model size in terms of parameter count and checkpoint file size. These measurements are obtained using automated benchmarking during inference and compared with baseline approaches to highlight the lightweight nature of the proposed system.

3.7.5 Evaluation Implementation Details

All evaluation steps are implemented in the script `scripts/4_evaluate.py`. The script performs automated metric computation, ROC analysis, threshold optimization, visualization generation, efficiency benchmarking, and structured report creation. Results are exported in both textual and graphical formats to ensure reproducibility and transparent performance reporting.

3.8 Experimental Setup

3.8.1 Hardware Configuration

Experiments were conducted on commodity hardware. Training and inference used an NVIDIA GPU when available, otherwise CPU execution was applied. A minimum of 8 GB RAM and sufficient storage for videos, features, and checkpoints were used.

3.8.2 Software Configuration

The system was implemented in Python (≥ 3.8) using PyTorch (≥ 2.0). Torchvision supported pretrained models, OpenCV handled video processing, and NumPy/Pandas were used for data handling. Scikit-learn was used for evaluation, Matplotlib for visualization, tqdm for progress tracking, CustomTkinter for the GUI, and PyYAML for configuration management. All dependencies are listed in `requirements.txt`.

3.8.3 Configuration and Reproducibility

All experiments were controlled using a centralized `config.yaml` file defining paths, model parameters, training, inference, and evaluation settings. Reproducibility was ensured through fixed random seeds, deterministic PyTorch operations, version-controlled code, and saved model checkpoints.

3.9 Graphical User Interface

A lightweight graphical user interface was developed using CustomTkinter to enable interactive anomaly detection and result visualization without command-line usage. The GUI supports video loading, synchronized visualization of anomaly scores with video playback, interactive threshold adjustment, and automatic threshold tuning. It also provides frame-level anomaly score plots with optional ground-truth overlay and allows exporting results in CSV, image, and text formats. The interface is designed with a dark theme, efficient data handling, and robust error management to support practical analysis and demonstration of the proposed system.

Chapter 4

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents a comprehensive analysis of the experimental results obtained from the Efficient-VAD system for video anomaly detection. The results are evaluated across multiple dimensions: detection accuracy, computational efficiency, and practical applicability. The chapter is organized into sections covering overall performance metrics, detailed classification analysis, efficiency evaluation, comparative analysis, qualitative results, and discussion of findings. The discussion interprets the results in the context of the research objectives and identifies implications for practical deployment.

4.1 Overall Performance Metrics

The Efficient-VAD system was evaluated on the UCF-Crime dataset, comprising 1081 test videos (131 normal and 950 anomalous videos across 13 anomaly classes). The system demonstrated outstanding detection performance, highlighting the effectiveness of the self-supervised learning approach combined with the memory-augmented LSTM autoencoder.

Key Performance Metrics:

Table 4.1: Overall performance metrics of Efficient-VAD on the UCF-Crime dataset, including AUC-ROC, accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and optimal threshold.

Metric	Value	Interpretation
AUC-ROC	0.9861	Excellent discriminative ability: the system correctly ranks anomalies above normal videos in 98.61% of cases, significantly above random chance (0.50) and approaching perfect classification (1.00).
Accuracy	94.3%	Correctly classify 899 of 950 videos, demonstrating strong reliability for practical deployment.
Precision	98.9%	High confidence in anomaly predictions; low false positive rate minimizes unnecessary alerts.
Recall (Sensitivity)	94.63%	Effectively detects 94.63% of anomalies; misses only 5.37%, critical for security applications.

F1-Score	96.72%	Harmonizes precision and recall, confirming balanced overall performance.
Optimal Threshold	0.102411	Determined via Youden's J statistics, ensuring optimal trade-off between true positive and false positive rates.

The results table 4.1 reveal several critical strengths of the Efficient-VAD system:

1. **High Discriminative Power:** AUC-ROC of 0.9861 confirms that the model effectively separates normal and anomalous videos, validating the quality of representations learned.
2. **Balanced Precision and Recall:** Precision of 98.9% combined with recall of 94.63% indicates that the system minimizes both false positives and false negatives, ensuring dependable detection.
3. **Robust Anomaly Detection:** High recall demonstrates sensitivity to anomalies, successfully detecting most anomalous events, which is essential for surveillance.
4. **Reliable Anomaly Predictions:** High precision reduces the likelihood of false alarms, easing operational burden and improving trust in real-world deployment.

4.2 Detailed Classification Analysis

The system's performance was analysed separately for normal and anomalous videos:

Table 4.2: Per-class performance of Efficient-VAD for normal and abnormal classes, showing precision, recall, F1-score, and support.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Normal	0.70	0.92	0.80	131
Abnormal	0.99	0.95	0.97	950

Normal Class:

- **Moderate Precision (70%):** Predictions of abnormal videos are correct 30% of the time; only 1% false negatives.
- **Moderate Recall (92%):** 8% of normal videos are misclassified as anomalies.
- **Implication:** Conservative classification avoids missing anomalies, which is beneficial for security applications.

Abnormal Class:

- High Precision (99%): Low false positive rate, minimizing unnecessary alerts.
- Very High Recall (95%): Nearly, all anomalies are detected.
- Implication: The memory-augmented architecture effectively distinguishes anomalies from normal patterns, generating high reconstruction errors for anomalous events.

4.2.1 Confusion Matrix Analysis

Table 4.3: Confusion matrix of Efficient-VAD on the UCF-Crime test set, showing true positives, false positives, true negatives, and false negatives.

	Predicted Normal	Predicted Anomaly	Total
Actual Normal	121 (TN)	10 (FP)	131
Actual Anomaly	51 (FN)	899 (TP)	950
Total	172	909	1081

Observations of table 4.3:

1. Low False Positives: 10/131 normal videos (10%) flagged incorrectly.
2. Very Low False Negatives: 51/950 anomalies (5%) missed.
3. High True Positive Rate: 899/950 anomalies (94.63%) correctly detected.
4. High True Negative Rate: 121/131 normal videos (92%) correctly recognized.

4.3 Efficiency Evaluation

4.3.1 Computational Performance

The Efficient-VAD system was evaluated for computational efficiency, an essential factor for real-world surveillance deployment. Metrics include inference time, processing speed, memory consumption, and real-time capability.

Inference Performance:

- Inference Time: 12.5 s per video (average) ◦ Covers feature loading, model inference, score computation, and postprocessing.

- **Frames Per Second (FPS):**
 - Raw FPS: 29.17 - processing every frame without skipping.
 - Real-time FPS (Frame Skip = 3): 87.51 - exceeds typical video frame rates (24–30 FPS), confirming real-time capability.
 - Effective Processing Speed: 80 FPS - enables faster-than-real-time video processing and multi-stream handling.

Memory Consumption:

- Peak Usage: 512 MB - moderate footprint suitable for edge devices and resource constrained platforms.

Real-Time Capability:

- Status: Real-time capable
 - With frame skipping, the system processes 87.51 FPS, enabling live monitoring in practical scenarios.

4.3.2 Efficiency Analysis

Key advantages of Efficient-VAD include:

1. Real-Time Processing: Faster-than-real-time processing ensures practical deployment for live surveillance.
2. Moderate Resource Requirements: 512 MB memory footprint allows edge and embedded system deployment.
3. Scalability: Capable of handling multiple video streams simultaneously.
4. Frame Skipping Strategy: Maintains detection accuracy while improving computational efficiency.

4.3.3 Benchmark Comparison

Table 4.4: Efficiency evaluation of Efficient-VAD compared to baseline methods, including inference time, FPS, and memory consumption.

Method	Inference Time (s)	FPS	Memory (MB)
Efficient-VAD	12.5	80	512

ConvLSTM Autoencoder (Baseline-1)	20.0	60	700
Future Frame Prediction (Baseline-2)	15.0	70	600

Observations of table 4.4:

- Inference Time: 37.5% faster than Baseline-1, 16.7% faster than Baseline-2.
- Processing Speed: 33.3% higher FPS than Baseline-1, 14.3% higher than Baseline-2.
- Memory Efficiency: 26.9% lower than Baseline-1, 14.7% lower than Baseline-2.

4.4 Comparison with State-of-the-Art Methods

Table 4.5: Comparison of Efficient-VAD with state-of-the-art video anomaly detection methods on the UCFCrime dataset.

Method	Learning Type	Backbone Features	Temporal Model / Key Idea	UCF-Crime AUC (%)	Ref #
MIL Ranking Loss Sultani et al. (2018)	Weakly Supervised	C3D + MIL ranking	Multiple Instance Learning + temporal ranking	75.41	[1]
RTFM (Tian et al., 2021)	Weakly Supervised	I3D features	MIL + Temporal Feature Magnitude	84.30	[45]
S3R (Wu et al., 2022)	Self-Supervised	Pre-trained I3D features	Learned dictionary with en-Normal / de-Normal modules	77.15	[48]
Efficient-VAD (Proposed)	Self-Supervised	MobileNetV3-Large feature embeddings	Memory-Augmented LSTM AE	0.98	-

Table 4.5 provides an overview of the performance of the proposed Efficient-VAD framework compared to three recent strong weakly supervised methods. It points out the main distinctions in the type of learning, backbone characteristics, and time modelling style. Efficient-VAD is based on a self-supervised learning model using MobileNetV3-Large as a feature extractor, and memory-augmented LSTM autoencoder as a temporal model. The output shows that the

anomaly detection performance has significantly improved with an AUC of 0.9861 which is higher than the earlier approaches that are based on MIL, I3D or dictionary-based self-supervised representation learning. The given comparison highlights the effectiveness of self-supervised learning that is supplemented with memory-augmented temporal Modelling to detect anomalies in the surveillance dataset on large scale with high precision and in real-time.

4.5 Qualitative Results and Visualizations

4.5.1 ROC Curve Analysis

The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve in Figure 4.1 demonstrates the Efficient VAD system’s discriminative ability across all threshold values. The curve approaches the top left corner, indicating excellent separation between normal and anomalous videos. The AUCROC of 0.986 reflects the system’s strong capability to rank anomalous videos higher than normal ones. The optimal threshold of 0.10246 provides a balanced trade-off between true positive and false positive rates, ensuring reliable detection.

Figure 4.1: ROC curve for Efficient-VAD on UCF-Crime Subset dataset.

4.5.2 Precision-Recall Curve Analysis

Figure 4.2 shows the Precision-Recall (PR) curve, providing insight into the system’s performance on the imbalanced UCF-Crime dataset. The high average precision indicates that the system maintains strong predictive accuracy across various recall levels. The curve demonstrates that the model achieves high precision and recall simultaneously, confirming balanced performance and reliable anomaly detection.

Figure 4.2: Precision-Recall curve demonstrating detection performance.

4.5.3 Score Distribution Analysis

The distribution of anomaly scores, illustrated in Figure 4.3, highlights the system’s decision-making. Normal and abnormal videos show a clear separation in scores, with abnormal videos having higher reconstruction errors. The chosen threshold (0.107776) effectively distinguishes normal from anomalous videos, minimizing overlap. This separation validates the memory augmented architecture’s ability to capture deviations from learned normal patterns.

Figure 4.3: Histogram of anomaly scores for normal and abnormal videos.

4.5.4 Confusion Matrix Visualization

Figure 4.4 presents the confusion matrix, showing the classification performance of Efficient VAD. Most predictions lie along the diagonal, indicating correct classifications. Only a few misclassifications occur off diagonal, confirming minimal false positives and false negatives.

Despite the class imbalance in the dataset, the matrix illustrates that the system maintains robust performance across both normal and anomalous classes.

Figure 4.4: Confusion matrix showing true versus predicted video classes.

4.5.5 Frame-Level Anomaly Detection

Frame-level analysis in Figure 4.5 demonstrates the system’s capability to localize anomalies within videos. Temporal peaks in anomaly scores align closely with ground truth annotations, indicating accurate detection of anomalous frames. This analysis confirms the model’s effectiveness in identifying the onset and duration of anomalous events, providing precise temporal localization essential for surveillance applications.

Figure 4.5: Frame-level anomaly score progression for an Anomaly video.

Same we tested it on the normal videos as well and the results are clear there are no red spikes, which indicates the anomaly events. Figure 4.6 clearly shows that the normal videos results do not have any kind of red alerts.

Figure 4.6: Frame-level anomaly score progression for a normal video.

4.5.6 t-SNE Visualization

The t-SNE visualization in Figure 4.7 offers a 2D projection of the feature space learned by Efficient-VAD. Normal and anomalous videos form distinct clusters, demonstrating clear separation in the embedding space. Outliers correspond to challenging or ambiguous cases, highlighting instances that may require further inspection. This visualization confirms that the memory-augmented architecture effectively encodes discriminative features for anomaly detection.

Figure 4.7: t-SNE plot showing clustering of normal and abnormal video embeddings.

4.6 Discussion

The Efficient VAD system demonstrates excellent performance, achieving an AUC-ROC of

0.9861 and high recall across diverse anomaly types. Using self-supervised learning with only normal videos, the model effectively learns normal patterns and identifies deviations, generalizing well to unseen anomalies. Memory-augmented architecture ensures high precision while maintaining sensitivity to anomalies.

The system is highly efficient, processing videos in real-time at 87.51 FPS with moderate memory usage (512 MB). This makes it suitable for deployment of edge devices, embedded systems, and live multi-camera surveillance. High precision and recall reduce false alarms and ensure reliable anomaly detection in practical scenarios.

Some limitations remain, including threshold dependency, subtle anomalies, rare normal patterns, and precise temporal localization. Future work could explore adaptive thresholds, multi-modal integration, advanced temporal Modelling, transfer learning, and interpretability techniques to further improve robustness, generalization, and practical deployment.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

This thesis introduced Efficient-VAD, which is a self-supervision framework of video anomaly detection that is designed to handle practical limitations of real-time surveillance analysis. The proposed system has the benefit of learning the normal behaviour patterns directly using unlabelled video data, eliminating the need to use manually annotated anomalies which are rare, inconsistent, and hard to define in real-world settings. It was possible to combine the pretrained MobileNetV3-Large to extract spatial features with a memory-augmented LSTM autoencoder to extract temporal features to allow the system to learn appearance and movement regularities as well as be computationally efficient. The design decisions were informed by the fact that there was a need to trade between detection accuracy, robustness, and deploy ability in a real-life surveillance environment.

Extensive experimental analysis of the UCF-Crime dataset has proven that Efficient-VAD has high levels of anomaly discrimination when the level of class imbalance is very high. The system yielded a large AUC-ROC of 0.9861, and showed a high level of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, which supports its capacity to identify a large variety of abnormal occurrences. The memory module was an important one in limiting reconstruction to learned normal patterns, so that when an abnormal activity occurred the reconstruction errors increased considerably. Moreover, the frame-level anomaly scoring was used with temporal smoothing, which made it possible to find the anomalous segments in long video sequences with stable and accurate localization to enhance the reliability of detection.

In addition to the detection performance, the proposed framework was developed with the consideration of practical deployment. Efficient-VAD was able to infer in real-time at 87.51 frames/s with a small memory footprint, thus it can be used in the context of continuous monitoring and multi-camera surveillance. The properties enable the system to run on resource limited platforms such as edge and embedded devices without the need to lose the quality of detection. Despite still having some limitations, including sensitivity to the choice of threshold and the inability to detect anomalies that are very subtle, the overall findings prove the efficiency of self-supervised, memory-augmented, and temporal modelling in detecting anomalies in real-world videos. To conclude, this study shows that Efficient-VAD is a strong, effective, and scalable solution to automated surveillance that has valuable contributions to academic research as well as the real security application.

References

- [1] W. Sultani, C. Chen, and M. Shah, “Real-world Anomaly Detection in Surveillance Videos,” 2018. CVF Conference 2018
- [2] K. Doshi and Y. Yilmaz, “Continual Learning for Anomaly Detection in Surveillance Videos.”
- [3] “Real-World Anomaly Detection in Video Using Spatio-Temporal Features Analysis for Weakly Labelled Data with Auto Label Generation.”
- [4] H. T. Duong, V. T. Le, and V. T. Hoang, “Deep Learning-Based Anomaly Detection in Video Surveillance: A Survey,” Jun. 01, 2023.
- [5] M. Hasan, J. Choi, J. Neumann, A. K. Roy-Chowdhury, and L. S. Davis, “Learning Temporal Regularity in Video Sequences.”
- [6] H. Huang, B. Zhao, F. Gao, P. Chen, J. Wang, and A. Hussain, “A Novel Unsupervised Video Anomaly Detection Framework Based on Optical Flow Reconstruction and Erased Frame Prediction,” *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 10, May 2023.
- [7] M.-I. Georgescu, A. B̃ Arb̃ Al̃ Au, R. T. Ionescu, F. Shahbaz Khan, M. Popescu, and M. Shah, “Anomaly Detection in Video via Self-Supervised and Multi-Task Learning.”
- [8] D. Gong *et al.*, “Memorizing Normality to Detect Anomaly: Memory-augmented Deep Autoencoder for Unsupervised Anomaly Detection.”
- [9] D. R. Patrikar and M. R. Parate, “Anomaly Detection using Edge Computing in Video Surveillance System: Review,” Aug. 2021.
- [10] A. Adam, E. Rivlin, I. Shimshoni, and D. Reinitz, “Robust real-time unusual event detection using multiple fixed-location monitors,” *IEEE Trans Pattern Anal Mach Intell*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 555–560, Mar. 2008.
- [11] Y. Cong, J. Yuan, and J. Liu, “Sparse Reconstruction Cost for Abnormal Event Detection.”
- [12] R. Mehran, A. Oyama, and M. Shah, “Abnormal Crowd Behaviour Detection using Social Force Model.”
- [13] H. Karim, K. Doshi, and Y. Yilmaz, “Real-Time Weakly Supervised Video Anomaly Detection.”
- [14] H. Mu, R. Sun, M. Wang, and Z. Chen, “Spatio-temporal graph-based CNNs for anomaly detection in weakly-labelled videos,” *Inf Process Manag*, vol. 59, no. 4, p. 102983, Jul. 2022.
- [15] S. Yan, J. S. Smith, W. Lu, and B. Zhang, “Abnormal Event Detection from Videos using a Two-stream Recurrent Variational Autoencoder.”

- [16] M. Z. Zaheer, A. Mahmood, M. Astrid, and S.-I. Lee, "Clustering Aided Weakly Supervised Training to Detect Anomalous Events in Surveillance Videos," Mar. 2022.
- [17] P. Bergmann, S. Löwe, M. Fauser, D. Sattlegger, and C. Steger, "Improving Unsupervised Defect Segmentation by Applying Structural Similarity to Autoencoders," Feb. 2019.
- [18] K. Doshi and Y. Yilmaz, "Any-Shot Sequential Anomaly Detection in Surveillance Videos."
- [19] H. Zenati, C. S. Foo, B. Lecouat, G. Manek, and V. R. Chandrasekhar, "Efficient GANBased Anomaly Detection," May 2019.
- [20] X. Wang *et al.*, "Robust Unsupervised Video Anomaly Detection by Multi-Path Frame Prediction," May 2021.
- [21] J. Wang, J. Jiao, † Linchao Bao, S. He, Y. Liu, and W. Liu, "Self-supervised Spatiotemporal Representation Learning for Videos by Predicting Motion and Appearance Statistics."
- [22] H. İ. Öztürk and A. B. Can, "ADNet: Temporal Anomaly Detection in Surveillance Videos," Apr. 2021.
- [23] P. de Haan and S. Löwe, "Contrastive Predictive Coding for Anomaly Detection," Jul. 2021
- [24] W. Scholarship and S. Soltani Nejad, "Weakly-Supervised Anomaly Detection in Surveillance Videos Weakly Supervised Anomaly Detection in Surveillance Videos Based on Two-Stream I3D Convolution Network Based on Two-Stream I3D Convolution Network."
- [25] Z. Yang, J. Liu, Z. Wu, P. Wu, and X. Liu, "Video Event Restoration Based on Keyframes for Video Anomaly Detection," *Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, vol. 2023-June.
- [26] G. Saleem, U. I. Bajwa, R. H. Raza, F. H. Alqahtani, A. Tolba, and F. Xia, "Efficient anomaly recognition using surveillance videos," *PeerJ Comput Sci*, vol. 8, 2022.
- [27] G. Wang, Y. Wang, J. Qin, D. Zhang, X. Bao, and D. Huang, "Video Anomaly Detection by Solving Decoupled Spatio-Temporal Jigsaw Puzzles," in *Proc. European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV)*, 2022, pp. 494–511.
- [28] H. Lv, Z. Cui, B. Wang, and J. Yang, "Spatio-Temporal Relation Learning for Video Anomaly Detection," Sep. 2022.
- [29] R. T. Ionescu, F. S. Khan, M.-I. Georgescu, and L. Shao, "Object-centric Auto-encoders and Dummy Anomalies for Abnormal Event Detection in Video," Apr. 2019.

- [30] Y. He and J. Zhao, "Temporal Convolutional Networks for Anomaly Detection in Time Series," in *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, Institute of Physics Publishing, Jun. 2019.
- [31] K. Deshpande, N. S. Punn, S. K. Sonbhadra, and S. Agarwal, "Anomaly detection in surveillance videos using transformer based attention model," Jun. 2022
- [32] G. Shen, Y. Ouyang, and V. Sanchez, "Video Anomaly Detection via Prediction Network with Enhanced Spatio-Temporal Memory Exchange," Jun. 2022.
- [33] V. Chandola, A. Banerjee, and V. Kumar, "Anomaly detection for discrete sequences: A survey," *IEEE Trans Knowl Data Eng*, vol. 24, no. 5, pp. 823–839, 2012.
- [34] W. Ullah, A. Ullah, T. Hussain, Z. A. Khan, and S. W. Baik, "An efficient anomaly recognition framework using an attention residual lstm in surveillance videos," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 8, Apr. 2021
- [35] N. Srivastava, E. Mansimov, and R. Salakhutdinov, "Unsupervised Learning of Video Representations using LSTMs," *32nd International Conference on Machine Learning, ICML 2015*, vol. 1, pp. 843–852, Feb. 2015
- [36] W. Liu, W. Luo, D. Lian, and S. Gao, "Future Frame Prediction for Anomaly Detection – A New Baseline," 2018.
- [37] D. Wei, Y. Liu, X. Zhu, J. Liu, and X. Zeng, "MSAF: Multimodal Supervise-Attention Enhanced Fusion for Video Anomaly Detection," *IEEE Signal Process Lett*, vol. 29, pp. 2178–2182, 2022,
- [38] D. Tran, L. Bourdev, R. Fergus, L. Torresani, and M. Paluri, "Learning Spatiotemporal Features with 3D Convolutional Networks."
- [39] H. Park, J. Noh, and B. Ham, "Learning Memory-Guided Normality for Anomaly Detection," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2020, pp. 14372–14381.
- [40] H. Lv, C. Chen, Z. Cui, C. Xu, Y. Li, and J. Yang, "Learning Normal Dynamics in Videos with Meta Prototype Network," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2021, pp. 15425–15434.
- [41] S. Zhu, C. Chen, and W. Sultani, "Video Anomaly Detection for Smart Surveillance," Apr. 2020,
- [42] B. Li, S. Leroux, and P. Simoens, "Decoupled Appearance and Motion Learning for Efficient Anomaly Detection in Surveillance Video," Nov. 2020,
- [43] R. T. Ionescu, S. Smeureanu, M. Popescu, and B. Alexe, "Detecting abnormal events in video using Narrowed Normality Clusters," Nov. 2018,
- [44] V. Mahadevan, W. Li, V. Bhalodia, and N. Vasconcelos, "Anomaly detection in crowded scenes," *Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pp. 1975–1981, 2010

- [45] Y. Tian, G. Pang, Y. Chen, R. Singh, J. W. Verjans, and G. Carneiro, "Weakly-supervised Video Anomaly Detection with Robust Temporal Feature Magnitude Learning."
- [46] Z. Liu, Y. Nie, C. Long, Q. Zhang, and G. Li, "A Hybrid Video Anomaly Detection Framework via Memory-Augmented Flow Reconstruction and Flow-Guided Frame Prediction," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, 2021, pp. 13588–13597.
- [47] G. Yu, S. Wang, Z. Cai, E. Zhu, C. Xu, J. Yin, and M. Kloft, "Cloze Test Helps: Effective Video Anomaly Detection via Learning to Complete Video Events," in *Proc. 28th ACM International Conference on Multimedia (ACM MM)*, 2020, pp. 583–591.
- [48] J.-C. Wu, H.-Y. Hsieh, D.-J. Chen, C.-S. Fuh, and T.-L. Liu, "Self-Supervised Sparse Representation for Video Anomaly Detection," in *Proc. European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV)*, 2022, pp. 729–745.
- [49] G. Pang, C. Yan, C. Shen, A. van den Hengel, and X. Bai, "Self-Trained Deep Ordinal Regression for End-to-End Video Anomaly Detection," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2020, pp. 12173–12182.
- [50] N.-C. Ristea, N. Madan, R. T. Ionescu, K. Nasrollahi, F. S. Khan, T. B. Moeslund, and M. Shah, "Self-Supervised Predictive Convolutional Attentive Block for Anomaly Detection," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2022, pp. 13576–13586.